

Co-ordination Chemistry of Quinquevalent Molybdenum-2,2-Bipyridyl and 1,10-Phenanthroline Complexes

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In continuation of our investigations^{1,2} on the co-ordination chemistry of quinquevalent molybdenum we would like to report here the isolation of non-electrolytic complexes of the bromo-series of the general formula $\text{MoO} \cdot \text{Br}_3 \cdot \text{L}$ (where L=2,2' bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline) like the corresponding chloro-series³ reported already by us. In both the cases our lines of investigations are identical and different from others^{5,6}.

Starting from the oxo-penta-bromo-molybdates (V) of 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline already reported by us⁴, we have isolated the compounds by simple dehydrohalogenation by refluxing in dehydrated ethanol and acetonitrile, and also by heating in solid states.

(where L=2,2'-Bipyridyl and 1,10-Phenanthroline)

Compound (a) has been isolated in two different forms (color varies from reddish pink to brown). Other compounds isolated in such investigations are,

Compounds (b) and (c) have also been isolated by simple metathesis from ethanolic solutions of $(\text{NH}_4)_2 [\text{MoOBr}_5]$ and 2,2'-bipyridyl. These compounds have been characterised by chemical analysis, magnetic susceptibility measurements, oxidation state determinations by ceric sulphate titrations and U.V. and I.R. spectra. Further work in this line is in progress and details will be published later on.

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